

TRIBOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF SINTERED AND FORGED ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES

A. P. Monteiro Baptista and Mário A. Pinto, INEGI - Fac. Eng./ Univ. Porto,
Rua dos Bragas, 4099 Porto Codex, Portugal

ABSTRACT

Lubricated block on ring wear tests of powder metallurgy (PM) particle reinforced 6061 aluminium composites, against steel, show an improved wear resistance when compared to the unreinforced matrix.

The influence of different material parameters, such as - reinforcement type (SiC or alumina), reinforcement volume fraction (10, 15 and 20%), ageing condition and intensity of the forging process - in the tribological behaviour of metal matrix composites have been studied. Wear rate and coefficient of friction results are presented and discussed.

Keywords: wear, friction, metal matrix composites

1. INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

During the last ten years the production of metal matrix composites (MMC) have been greatly expanded. Squeeze casting by preform infiltration for local reinforcement of critical parts, is one of the technics which have been developed. Powder metallurgy (PM) routes, using fiber, platelets or particulate reinforcements to obtain near-net shape parts, are promising alternatives.

For the production of a particular item, the replacement of one conventional material requires that the new one - the replacement- meets and extends the relevant properties of the replaced or that its production costs are reduced without significant loss of quality. In the case of the application of MMC's, the production costs are generally higher then those of the conventional technics. So, the final product must show better properties or else it will not be useful.

The expectancy of improvement by the use of MMC's, is focused on the high temperature behaviour and tribological properties. In both cases, the hard, refractory particles or fibers of the reinforcement enhance the properties of a softer matrix, allowing higher temperatures and loads to be used.

We have studied the wear behaviour, in dry rectilinear reciprocating sliding, of aluminium matrix composites against gray cast iron [1]. We have shown that under those conditions the composites could present, in some cases, a worst behaviour, due to the presence and effect of the hard abrasive fibers. The results of lubricated block on cylinder wear tests of particle reinforced 6061 aluminium composites, against steel, clearly show an improved wear resistance when compared to the unreinforced matrix.

2. - TESTED MATERIALS

The aim of the present work was the study of the influence of different material parameters - *reinforcement type, reinforcement volume fraction, ageing condition and intensity of the forging process* - in the tribological behaviour of metal matrix composites. For comparative purposes we

also tested the unreinforced matrix.

2.1.-Aluminium and MMC blocks

Tested materials were 6061 aluminium alloys (1.0% Mg, 0,6%Si, 0,25% Cu, 0,25%Cr), wrought alloy, PM type and reinforced with different particles and volume fractions, as listed in table 1.

Table 1. Block materials. Composition and condition.

Material	reinforcement	volume fraction	condition
Al-	none	0 %	T6
Al 6061 PM-	none	0 %	T6
20 % SiC.	SiC	20 %.	T6
20%SiC.n	SiC	20 %.	as forged
10 % SiC.	SiC	10 %.	T6
10%SiC.n	SiC	10 %.	as forged
15 % SiC.	SiC	15 %.	T6 *
15%SiC.n	SiC	15 %.	as forged
20 % Al ₂ O ₃ .	Al ₂ O ₃	20 %.	T6
20%Al ₂ O ₃ .n	Al ₂ O ₃	20 %.	as forged
10 % Al ₂ O ₃ .	Al ₂ O ₃	10 %.	T6
10%Al ₂ O ₃ .n	Al ₂ O ₃	10 %.	as forged
Mix. (10+10)	Al ₂ O ₃ +SiC	(10 +10) %.	T6
Mix.(10+10).n	Al ₂ O ₃ +SiC	(10 +10) %.	as forged

* 160° - 18 hours

The T6 treatment correspond to a 530° C salt bath solution treatment, followed by water quenching and ageing. The peak ageing condition, experimentally determined for these materials [2], consisting in 4 hours at 175° C, was generally used.

In the Table 2 relevant mechanical properties of some of those materials are presented. Unfortunately they are not available for the as forged composites and for the 10 and 15 % volume fraction. The tribological behaviour of the materials being greatly dependent on its mechanical properties, it is important to know them, in order to predict, or at least to explain, the observed results.

Table 2. Mechanical properties

		Al 6061 Wr.	Al 6061 PM	SiC - 20%	Al ₂ O ₃ - 20%	Mix(10+10)
		T6	T6	T6	T6	T6
Yield stress 0,2%	MPa	310	347	372	318	357
Ult. ten. stress	MPa	275	386	409	361	391
Young modulus	GPa	70	70	89	95	94
Elongation	%	12	14,4	1,3	4,1	1,6
Hardness	HB	95	118	-	-	-

2.2 Counterpart material

The cylinder material is a carbon steel (0,45% carbon content - DIN Ck 45 - 205 HB) finished by turning to a center line average -cla- not exceeding 1µm (Ra≤1µm).

3. TRIBOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION

3.1. Equipment and test piece geometry

Wear tests were performed in an air conditioned laboratory at 60±5 % relative humidity and 20±3° C room temperature, using the block on ring tribometer, presented in schema on figure 1, with the following parameters:

- Loads- All the composites 1200 N (in some cases also 673 N, as for the matrix).

- Sliding speed- 1,5 m/s (turning velocity of 240 rpm).
- Test length- 1,885Km (5000 revolutions).
- Lubricant- New motor oil (Shell Helix -15W50) for each set of 7 tests (same composite or block material and same ring).
- Test block dimensions- (11,5x3x6) mm³.
- Counterpart geometry- cylinder (ø120x30), turned to an average roughness of about Ra=0,8 mm.

The loads were applied over a flat nominal surface of 34,5mm² (11,5x3) by dead weights, and the contact pressure decreased from very high values (theoretically linear contact at the beginning of the test) to final values depending on material's wear and shape changes.

Fig. 1 Schematic view of the block on ring tribometer

The wear rates were calculated from the apparent final contact area, by computing the volume loss which was transformed to weight loss, using the density of the materials. These calculations were made from the dimensions of the apparent final contact area, measured in a metrological microscope.

Two types of test were performed: a non stop 5000 revolutions test and an interrupted test, stopping after 250, 500, 1250, 2500 and 5000 turns for measuring the evolution of the wear process. In the first case, we can only present the mean wear rate or the total volume loss for the entire sliding distance. For the interrupted test, the cumulative mass or volume loss curve, show the typical intense variation of the wear rate - very high slope at the beginning -“running-in”- and small slope when the steady state conditions are reached.

3.2.-Wear rates in lubricated tests

Figures 2 to 6 show the wear behaviour of the matrix (reference material) and composites. The wear rates of the reinforced materials are smaller than those of the unreinforced reference materials, both wrought and PM alloys.

Some informations can be derived from the Figure 2. For the tests under 680 N, all the 20% volume fraction composites present a much lower wear rate than the reference materials, the alumina reinforced composite being the best one. The three deformation degrees - 45, 54 or 78% of high reduction in the open die forging operation - doesn't give very significant differences in the wear

rates. The 1200 N tests confirm the better wear behaviour of the alumina reinforced composites, either in the T6 or in the as forged condition. As it was expected, the T6 treatment improves the wear resistance of the SiC and alumina reinforced composites.

Fig. 2 Mean wear rate of 20% volume fraction composites and reference materials. Applied load 680 or 1200N; Block on ring; 1800m sliding distance; lubricated (Shell Helix) 45 - 54 or 78 high reduction (%) in the forging operation; n.- as forged condition else T6

3.2.1 - SiC reinforced composites - T6 treatment, deformation and volume fraction.

The effect of the heat treatment is clearly visible in Figure 3, corresponding to the evolution of the wear loss of the 10% SiC reinforced composite. During running-in, till about 500 revolutions, there is no significant difference between the wear loss of the treated and the as forged composites.

Fig. 3 Cumulative wear loss of 10% SiC reinforced composites. Applied load 1200N; Block on ring; 1800m sliding distance; lubricated (Shell Helix) N - as forged condition; T -T6

For longer sliding distance this difference tends to increase, reaching more than 25% at the end of the test. The higher ductility and lower hardness of the as forged material are responsible for its lower wear resistance and this fact will be observed for the other materials.

The intensity of the deformation process during the forging operation is expected to improve the mechanical properties of the materials. In fact, PM composites are hardly produced in full density and more extensive plastic deformation tends to reduce the total volume of defects within the body, so increasing its strength. In the Figure 4, it is shown the evolution of the wear loss during the interrupted test of three types of the 15% SiC reinforced composites, forged to - 33, 58 and 60 % high reduction, in an open die operation.

There are not significant differences between the wear behaviour of the two last ones (almost the same deformation degree) but they diverge at a very important factor in respect to the 33% high reduction composite. It seems that the smaller deformation is insufficient to achieve the full result.

For the 20% SiC reinforced composites, Figure 5, the effect of the treatment on the wear loss confirms the observed behaviour for the 10% composite. The single point result for the test under 673 N indicates the usual influence of the load on the wear loss.

Fig. 4 Cumulative wear loss of 15% SiC reinforced composites T6 treated. Applied load 1200N; Block on ring; 1800m sliding distance; lubricated (Shell Helix) 33, 58 and 60% height reduction in the open die forging operation.

The three curves shown in the Figure 6, represent the best results for the 10, 15 and 20% SiC reinforced MMC's - 10% volume fraction of reinforcement seems to be not enough to provide a better wear behaviour (insufficient hardness allowing plastic deformation) and 20% volume fraction of reinforcement seems to be too much (more difficult consolidation of the composite and decohesion under load, increasing abrasive activity of SiC particles). The single point results for tests under 673 N show the influence of the load on the total wear loss. Almost equivalent for the 10% SiC composite under 1200 N and the PM reference material under 673 N.

3.3. -Wear rates of the steel counterpart

The wear loss of the steel counterpart in these lubricated wear tests haven't been measured in a systematic way. However, some observations using a surface roughness meter apparatus, indicate that the volume loss is generally greater against the alumina reinforced composites, when tested under identical conditions. This fact might be related to the more brittle characteristics of the SiC particles, which tends to be crushed as in a high stress abrasion process, or rounded, losing part of its abrasiveness.

The unreinforced material produces practically no wear on the steel ring.

Fig. 5 Cumulative wear loss of 20% SiC reinforced composites
Applied load 1200N (or 673N); Block on ring; 1800m sliding distance; lubricated (Shell Helix)
N - as forged condition; T -T6

Fig. 6 Cumulative wear loss of 10, 15 and 20% SiC reinforced composites and matrix.
Applied load 1200N (or 673N); Block on ring; 1800m sliding distance; lubricated (Shell Helix)

3.4. -Friction coefficients

The more common friction behaviour is represented in a schematic form in the Figure 7. At the beginning of the test, the friction force is generally high, and so is its scatter. After some time, depending on the test conditions and materials, the friction force decrease to lower values indicating a more stable friction process, that can be due to a transition from a boundary lubrication to a full hydrodynamic friction regime. In some cases, moment raising in the friction force occurs, as at about 650 and 2850 revolutions in the schema, as result of a more severe interaction between the block and the ring. At those transient stages the lubricant film should be broken allowing the metal contact to occur.

In the alumina reinforced composites, on the contrary, the friction force tends to grow with the sliding distance. The cutting process on the steel ring should play an important role in this case.

To establish the friction coefficient for a particular test, the area under the friction curve was computed and then divided by the sliding distance, giving a weighted mean value. The results, for some of the tested materials, are presented in the Figure 8. In general, softer materials present lower values for the coefficient of friction. This fact is related to the extension of the running-in process, which is longer for the more wear resistant materials, and also to the depth of the interaction with the steel counterpart.

Fig. 7 Evolution of the friction coefficient during one test. Schema.

Fig. 8 Friction coefficients of aluminium alloys and composites against steel. Applied load 1200N (or 680N); Block on ring; 1800m sliding distance; lubricated (Shell Helix)

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The results presented in the previous points confirm some of the expected behaviour for this type of materials. As in dry abrasive tests, [3,4] the ageing treatment and the use of ceramic reinforcements increases the wear resistance. The higher hardness is generally thought to be the responsible for this improvement. However, increasing the volume fraction of the reinforcement doesn't lead, invariably, to better tribological properties [4]. As we saw, for the SiCp composite 15% volume fraction give lower wear rate than 20% volume fraction under identical conditions.

The wear mechanism involves intense plastic deformation, which could be partially prevented by the reduction in the ductility of the material caused by the SiC particles. The fracture at the particle-matrix interface, weakening the composite, allow higher wear rates.

The better result of the alumina reinforced composites might be related to the previous statements. In fact, there is a general understanding that alumina particles are more tough, resulting in stronger composites. A more detailed study, including SEM observation of the worn surfaces is still in progress and we hope that it will give in-depth information about the wear mechanisms of these materials.

The present stage of the work allow however some conclusions to be drawn, for the conditions of test that were used:

1. The ageing treatment and the use of ceramic reinforcements increases the wear resistance of the 6061 aluminium alloy, in lubricated block on ring wear tests.
2. Increasing the volume fraction of the reinforcement doesn't lead, invariably, to less wear rate.
3. Alumina reinforced composites show less wear loss than SiC ones, but they induce higher wear on the steel counterpart.
4. Two friction regimes were observed for all the materials with a transition from boundary lubrication to full hydrodynamic friction regime.

Acknowledgements

This project is financed by JNICT - Junta Nacional de Investigação Científica e Tecnológica, and is conducted as a cooperative research program with "LNETI-Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia e Tecnologia Industrial" (Lisbon), where the composites have been produced and treated.

References

1. Baptista, A.M., Neto, R., Duarte, J., Magalhães, A. B., *Influence of Reinforcement on the Tribological Behaviour of an Aluminum Alloy*, Chicago, Sep. "1988 World Materials Congress", in "CAST REINFORCED METAL COMPOSITES" Ed S. G. Fishman, A. K. Dhingra. ASM International, pp 361-366.
2. Carvalhinhos, H., Carvalho, M.H., Marcelo, T., *Comparative properties of Al 6061/SiC_p and Al 6061/Al₂O_{3p} Composites produced by a sintering and forging route*, S. Francisco, Jun.21-26 "1992 PM World Congress".
3. Wang, A., Rack, H. J., *The Effect of Ageing on the Abrasion Behavior of SiCw/2124 Metal Matrix Composites*, METAL & CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES, Ed. Bhagat, Clauer, Kumar, Ritter, The Minerals, Metals and Materials Society, 1990 pp 487-498.
4. Hutchings, *Wear of MMCs and CMCs*, University of Cambridge, 1991 pp 1-27